

PHOTOLYTIC SEPARATION OF URANIUM FROM VANADIUM

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The separation of uranium from vanadium has been carried out by photolysis in sunlight. For this purpose, solution mixtures of uranyl sulphate and vanadyl sulphate or ammonium vanadate, containing formic acid and ethanol, were exposed to sunlight. Pure uranium was precipitated in the form of the hydrated oxysulphate, leaving vanadium in solution. The influence of H^+ -ion concentration, time period of exposure, and the percentage composition of ethanol on the recovery of uranium has been investigated.

Harris and Kolthoff (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1484) isolated a compound of composition $UOSO_4 \cdot 8H_2O$ by photolysis of uranyl sulphate in presence of excess of sulphuric acid and 40% ethanol on exposure to sunlight. While it took them several days for isolating their compound, Sahoo and Patnaik (this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 483) readily obtained $UOSO_4 \cdot 3.3H_2O$ on exposing a solution of uranyl sulphate in presence of formic acid and ethanol to sunlight. This fact clearly indicates that the compounds obtained by the two sets of workers are not the same. The compound, isolated by us under the conditions reported by Harris and Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*), on analysis provides the formula $U(SO_4)_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ and M.W. 502, as already reported by Meyer and Nachod (*Annalen*, 1924, **440**, 186).

This compound, when left in a desiccator for about a week, undergoes dehydration, producing the compound having M.W. 492 to which Harris and Kolthoff attributed the formula $UOSO_4 \cdot 8H_2O$, and M.W. 494. As they were interested in the polarographic determination of uranium, obviously they did not ascertain the exact composition of the compound isolated by them since uranium to sulphate ratio was not mentioned.

This photolytic isolation of the $UOSO_4 \cdot 3.3H_2O$ has been adopted for the separation of uranium from vanadium. While ethanol has been used as the reducing agent, as also for the purpose of precipitation, formic acid serves the purpose of maintaining the required pH in preventing hydrolysis and also of a reducing agent. The yield and purity of uranium recovered by the method depend on such factors like variation of pH, the period of exposure to sunlight, the ratio of uranium to vanadium, and the percentage composition of ethanol in the solution. These factors within wide range of variation have been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Uranyl nitrate and vanadyl sulphate of E. Merck E.P. quality, and ammonium vanadate of B.D.H. quality were used. Uranyl sulphate was prepared from the nitrate and was made free of the mineral acid. Stock solutions of uranium and vanadium salts containing small amounts of formic acid to prevent hydrolysis were used. Solution mixtures of uranyl sulphate and ammonium vanadate or vanadyl sulphate of known U_3O_8 and V_2O_5 content were prepared. To this mixture formic acid was added to bring the solution to required pH, after which ethanol was added to have the necessary ethanolic composition. The total volume of the solution was always 100 c.c. The solutions were then exposed to sunlight when uranium was precipitated as the hydrated oxysulphate. After the required period of exposure, the precipitate was filtered, washed, and analysed for the recovery and purity of uranium as reported previously (Singh, Sahoo and Patnaik, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1959, **50A**, 129). Vanadium was analysed colorimetrically (Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Vol III, pp. 443-44, Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York).

Gopala Rao *et al.* (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1956, 150, 178) found that exposure of an hour to bright sunlight was sufficient for the reduction of uranium (VI) to uranium (IV) present as sulphate in H_2SO_4 (dil.) with ethanol. Presence of vanadium was found to require enhanced period of exposure. From Table I it appears that the recovery of uranium increases with the increase in the period of exposure for a 40% ethanolic composition of pH 2.1-2.3, U_2O_5 to V_2O_5 ratio being 500.1 to 153.4 and 500.1 to 225.1. The increase of vanadium ratio in the mixture appears also to diminish the percentage recovery of uranium under similar conditions. Duration of exposure for at least 15 hours is therefore considered necessary for the usual vanadium content, associated with uranium. It can also be found in the same table that when the pH is 2.1-2.3, percentage of recovery of uranium is always more than that when the pH is 1. It has been found, however, that the uranium obtained at pH 3 and above is contaminated with vanadium.

TABLE I
40 % Ethanol composition by volume.

Comp. of the mixture U_2O_5 .	calc. as oxides. V_2O_5 .	pH.	% Recovery of uranium with period of exposure for		
			2 Hrs.	4 Hrs.	15 Hrs.
500.1 mg.	153.4 mg.	1.0	33.94	45.60	82.72
"	"	2.1-2.3	39.88	76.74	90.68
"	225.1	1.0	8.56	10.68	53.96
"	"	2.1-2.3	19.32	49.88	63.52

A series of mixtures, having different alcoholic compositions by volume, within the pH range 2.1 to 2.3 was next exposed to sunlight to study the influence of alcohol. The data recorded in Table II show that the recovery of uranium is influenced by the composition of alcohol. The yield increases very appreciably with increase of alcohol composition up to 40% after which the yield diminishes. At 40% ethanolic composition the recovery is about 92% while at 60% ethanol it is about 96%.

TABLE II

Comp. of the mixture U_2O_5 .	calc. as oxides. V_2O_5 .	% Comp. of EtOH.	Uranium recovered estimated as U_2O_5 by		% Recovery.
			Ignition.	Jones reductor.	
454.0 mg.	98.15 mg.	10	117.6 mg.	117.0 mg.	25.90
"	"	20	326.6	325.0	71.93
"	"	30	380.8	380.5	83.87
"	"	40	416.4	415.8	91.70
"	"	50	426.8	424.6	93.99
"	"	60	434.4	433.3	95.68

This photochemical process has been applied to the separation of uranium from a number of elements including rare-earths and thorium, which will be published in due course.